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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

**AN ANALYTICAL DISCOURSE ON THE CONCEPT OF IMPEACHMENT
UNDER THE NIGERIAN CONSTITUTION**

By

Sani Abdullahi*

Abstract

The concept of impeachment entails one of the means through which the executive powers are put in check. This is because through the concept, the tenure of the President, Vice and President, Governor, or Deputy Governor could be brought to premature end. However, there appears to be widespread misconception as to its precise meaning, nature and legal effect under the Nigerian constitution. This could be found in public discourses, political analyses, legal researches and judicial proceedings. Using the doctrinal method of legal research, this article aimed to discovering the exact meaning, nature and legal effect of impeachment under the Nigerian constitution. One of the major findings is that the misunderstanding of the legal effect of impeachment is not unconnected to the silence of the constitution on the issue. There is no provision on what will become of the office holder after his removal through impeachment. It is accordingly recommended that the constitution should provide that the removal of the office holders through impeachment does not subject them to any legal disability with a proviso that this does not prevent further prosecution of the office holders where the grounds for the impeachment constitute offences under the Nigerian law.

Keywords: Impeachment, Removal, and Nature and legal effect of impeachment under the Constitution.

1.1 Introduction

Impeachment has been recognized as one of the legitimate means through which the President, Vice President, Governor, or Deputy Governor can be removed from office.¹ Even though it is a constitutional provision, it may have the effect of subversion of the mandate freely given by the electorates.² It plays no less a role than an electioneering process as it equally leads to institution of new President, Vice President, Governor, or Deputy Governor as the case may be.³ In fact some scholars argue that it is worse than a coup in that a coup is clearly against democratic principles, but impeachment is based on a legal cloak.⁴ In modern democratic society, it is the most effective check on the executive power.⁵

The Nigerian constitutional democracy is incomplete without mention of impeachment proceedings due to their threat to the fabrics of democratic governance. The most notable impeachment proceedings in the second republic resulted in the removal of the then executive Governor of Kaduna State, Late Abdulqadir Balarabe Musa in 1981. After the return of democracy in 1999, Nigeria witnessed a gale of impeachment or threats thereof never before in its history. In fact, there was no state which did not experience threat or actual impeachment proceedings from 1999 to date. Thus, Governors such as Rashid Ladoja of Oyo State; Joshua Dariye of Plateau State; Peter Obi of Anambra State; D.S.P. Alamieyeseigha of Bayelsa State; Murtala Nyako of Adamawa State; could not survive impeachment proceedings as it resulted to their removals. Other victims include Deputy Governors such Garba Gadi of Bauchi State; Sani Abubakar Danladi of Taraba State; Ali Olanusi of Ondo State; Peremobowei Ebebi of Bayelsa State to mention just a few.

However, notwithstanding its importance, there appears to be widespread misconception as to its precise meaning, nature and legal effect of impeachment under the Nigerian constitution. This could be found in public discourses, political analyses,

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² Charles Arinze Obiora and Malachy Chukwuemeka, 'Constitutionalism, Democracy and Impeachment in Nigeria (1999-2007): An Appraisal', *Journal of Constitutional Development*, (2012) 9 (6) 47.

³ Yekini Abubakar Olakulehun and Owolabani Mausi Olafunmilayo, 'The Gale of Impeachments in Nigeria: A Threat to Sustainable Democracy', in *Cross-cutting Issues in Nigerian Law: Essays in Honour of Funsho Adaramola*, (2009) 131.

⁴ Jordy C.B., et. al., *Checking Executive Power: Presidential Impeachment in Comparative Perspective*, (London: Preager, 2003), 152.

⁵ Ibid.

and legal and judicial proceedings. Even scholars on constitutional law are sometimes found guilty of this misunderstanding. The misconception mostly arises on the meaning of the words “impeachment” and “removal”. For instance, a justice of the Nigerian Supreme Court stated that the Nigerian Constitution does not make provisions for impeachment but only recognizes removal.⁶ The legal effects of impeachment are also a subject of misunderstanding in Nigeria. For instance, the House of Assembly passed a resolution to grant pardon to a State Deputy Governor following his removal through impeachment.⁷ In some other cases, the competence of a candidate to contest for election had been challenged on the ground of impeachment.⁸ Thus, using the doctrinal method of legal research, the objective of this paper is to discover the exact meaning, nature and legal effect of impeachment as provided under the Nigerian constitution.

1.2 Meaning of Impeachment

There is divergent views as to the meaning of impeachment⁹ and its difference, if any, with removal.¹⁰ This is why impeachment may slightly mean a different thing under different constitutions even though there are basic and universal elements inherent in it. It is not surprising, therefore, that it is sometimes defined in accordance with constitutional provisions. Impeachment has been defined as the accusation and prosecution of a person for treason, or other crimes and misdemeanors. It is also the prosecution of a person or commoner by the House of Commons, at the Bar of the House of Lords for treason, high crimes and misdemeanors.¹¹ Another definition in this line is that it is the procedure by which a minister of the Crown may be tried in front of his peers in parliament.¹² All these definitions have connotation with either

⁶ Per Niki Tobi JSC in *Inajoku v Adeleke* (2007) LPELR 10354

⁷ The Lagos State House of Assembly pardoned Mr. Femi Pedro following his impeachment about ten years ago on the ground that he had shown enough remorse.

⁸ *PDP vs. INEC* (1999) 11 NWLR (pt. 262) 200

⁹ John Murphy, *The Impeachment Process* (New York: Infobase Publishing, 2007) 7; Cletus Eze ‘A Critical Appraisal of the Procedure for the Impeachment of Elected Public Officers under the 1999 Nigerian Constitution’ *Unizik Law Journal*, (2007) 1 (2) 112.

¹⁰ For instance even in the United States, prior to Clinton impeachment case many citizens could not distinguish impeachment from removal hence considered them one and the same thing. See Jordy, et. al., (note 4) 2.

¹¹ Anandan Krishnan, *Words, Phrases and Maxims: Legally and Judicially Defined*, (Singapore: Lexis Nexis, 2008), 149. See also Chandrachud Y. V., *The Law Lexicon, The Encyclopedic Law Dictionary*, 2nd ed. (India: Wadhwa & Company, 2004), 880.

¹² Sheila Bone, *Osborne’s Concise Law Dictionary*, 9th ed. (London: Sweet & Maxwell) 198.

the United Kingdom or United States Constitutions. To put it more precisely and concisely, impeachment based on the above definitions entails the trial of public office holders for crimes (allegedly committed while holding the office) before legislative house which may lead to their removal from the public office. These definitions are restrictive in that they make reference, albeit indirectly, to particular constitutions. A general and more encompassing definition is that impeachment is the act (by legislature) of calling for removal of a public official, accomplished by presenting a written charge of the official's alleged misconduct.¹³

Describing how impeachment should best be understood, an author linked it to a criminal trial where accusations are made, investigations into wrong doings are conducted, charges are preferred and the "suspect" is tried in a court of law.¹⁴ In other words, it entails the entire processes of the accusations and investigations of acts of misconduct against a public officer for the purpose of proving the said allegation and consequently removing him from the office.

From the above definitions, impeachment is a process while removal is a possible end product of the process. Therefore, a public officer could be impeached but not removed because he was not found guilty of the misconduct leveled against him or that the required number of the lawmakers in support of the resolution for his removal has not being met. In the United States, for instance, an author asserted that from 1789, about 17 federal officers were impeached but only 7 were actually removed.¹⁵ These actually showed the difference between impeachment and removal.

In the Nigerian context, there appears to be misunderstanding of the concept of impeachment among a higher percentage of people from the media, general public, and even in the legal profession (lawyers and judges alike). This is because the words "impeachment" and "removal" are carelessly used in public affairs commentaries, legal researches and discourses, and also in judicial processes and pronouncements. Consequently, we identify two schools of thought as to the meaning and use of the two words. The first school considers and used impeachment and removal interchangeably. To them, impeachment and removal meant one and the same thing i.e. removing one from public office. The second school is of the view that

¹³ Garner B. A., *Black's Law Dictionary*, (St. Paul, Minn: West Publishing Co., 2009) 678.

¹⁴ John Murphy, (note 8) 8.

¹⁵ *Ibid*, 12.

impeachment is different from removal. According to it, impeachment is a process which may lead to removal when the office holder is found guilty of misconduct. This means that impeachment actually entails a process while the end product is the removal. It is a means to an end and not the end in itself. It is the process whereby elected executives are tried for misconduct by the representatives of the people resulting in their removal from office.¹⁶ The nature of this usage has been pointed out in the following words:

The correct legal sense of **impeach** refers only to the bringing of formal charges against an official. Since the purpose of impeachment is the removal from office of an official who has engaged in misconduct, many people focus on the intended result and use **impeach** to mean “to remove (public official) from office”. This sense is likely to cause confusion, and people should be aware of the word’s proper legal meaning.¹⁷

In the same vein, the usage does not escape the “eagle eye” of David Bernard Guralnik as such he properly captured it in the following words:

When an irate citizen demands that a disfavored citizen public official be impeached, the citizen clearly intends for the official to be removed from office. This popular use of impeach as a synonym of “throw out” (even if by due process) does not accord with the legal meaning of the word. When a public official is impeached, that is, formally accused of wrongdoing, this is only the start of what can be a lengthy process that may or may not lead to the official’s removal from office. In strict usage, an official is impeached (accused), tried, and then convicted or acquitted. The vaguer use of impeach reflects disgruntled citizens’ indifference to whether the official is forced from office by legal means or chooses to resign to avoid further disgrace.¹⁸

¹⁶ Owoede M. A., ‘Impeachment of Chief Executives under the 1999 Constitution: New Problems, New Solutions’ *The Journal of Constitutional Development*, (2007) 1 (3) 23.

¹⁷ David Bernard Guralnik, *Webster’s New World College Dictionary* (New York: Random House Inc., 2010) 34.

¹⁸ Samuel Johnson, *Dictionary of the English Language* (Boston: Houghton Mifflin Harcourt Publishing Co., 2016) 24.

To the best of our understanding, the view of the second school is the correct meaning of impeachment and removal under the Nigerian constitution.

1.3 The Usage of Impeachment under the Nigerian Constitution

The usage of impeachment and its relationship with removal under the Nigerian constitution had given rise to a lot of controversy. In fact, it was argued that in Nigeria, proceedings initiated by the legislature for the removal of some officers is popularly termed as impeachment although the word impeachment has never being used anywhere in the constitution”.¹⁹ In other instances, impeachment and removal have mostly been used interchangeably and carelessly in some constitutional texts, legal discourses, by the media, and general public. Thus, it is important to point out how the constitution uses the word “impeachment”. In the entire provisions of the constitution, the word appears only in two related provisions dealing with circumstances under which the office of the President and Governor becomes vacant and empowers the Vice President and Deputy Governor to take over respectively.²⁰ However, the provisions dealing with impeachment of the President, Vice President, Governor and Deputy Governor do not mention the word “impeachment”. This appears to be the basis of the controversy and misunderstanding of the usage of impeachment under the Nigerian constitution which made a justice of the Supreme Court to opine that it is not recognized by the constitution. To him, what we have is removal as it is what the constitution categorically uses. He made bold to add further:

Impeachment is defined in Black's Law Dictionary as "a criminal proceeding against a public officer, before a quasi-political court, instituted by a written accusation called articles of impeachment; for example, a written accusation of the House of Representatives of the United States to the Senate of the United States against the President, Vice President or an officer of the United State including Federal Judges". This definition, with a slant for the United States Constitution, does not totally reflect the content of section 188 of the 1999 Constitution, as it conveys so much element of criminality. Section 188 is not so worded. The section covers both civil and

¹⁹ Ehipany Azinge, ‘Legislative Adjudication: Uses and Abuses’, in Okon E., *Lawmaking Process in Nigeria*, (Benin: UNIBEN Press, 2009) 161.

²⁰ See sections 191 and 146 of the constitution.

criminal conduct. Therefore the word should not be used as a substitute for the removal provisions of section 188 and the section 188 procedure should simply be referred to as one for removal of Governor or Deputy Governor...²¹

The above understanding of the Supreme Court on what the word impeachment entails is wrong for the following reasons. First, the court, having realized correctly that the definition above was given in relation to United States constitution, fails to understand that the definition only pointed out the grounds of impeachment under the constitution of the United States of America. The definition does not take into cognizance the varying grounds of impeachment under some other constitutions. It is, therefore, restrictive in scope and cannot be the yardstick for determining what impeachment entails generally. If we were to go by this definition and the understanding, it would mean that any country whose constitution does not recognize these as grounds of impeachment has no impeachment in its provisions. The fallacy of this view is that the meaning of impeachment is tied to the grounds of impeachment only.

Secondly, impeachment is a power given to the legislature with an enshrined procedure to be followed in the exercise of the power. Once the power is vested on the legislature by a constitution and the procedure for exercising it as specified is the same as the procedure for impeachment, then it qualifies as impeachment. The fact that the word impeachment does not appear in any of the constitutional provisions does not take anything away from it. This is because it is not every constitutional concept that bears its name in the relevant constitutional provision or its head or side notes. For instance, the words “rule of law” and “separation of powers” do not appear in the constitutional provision relating to rule of law and separation of powers. However, the concepts have been enshrined in various provisions of the Nigerian constitution.

Thirdly, the judge closed his eyes to the fact that the same constitution he was referring to had expressly made reference to impeachment although in a manner that twists its meaning. The Constitution provides for impeachment as one of the ways through which the office of the President²² or Governor²³ may become vacant. It recognizes

²¹ Per Niki Tobi JSC in *Inajoku v Adeleke* (2007) LPELR 10354

²² Section 146 of the Constitution.

²³ *Ibid*, Section 191.

impeachment, incapacity, death and removal as circumstances under which the Vice President could take over power from the President and the Deputy Governor from the Governor of a State as discussed in greater details in the next part of the paper.²⁴ However, apart from this section, there is no any other place in the constitution where impeachment is mentioned as a means to bring to premature end the tenure of the President, Vice President Governor, or Deputy Governor. This equally goes to show that impeachment is recognized by the Nigerian constitution. Therefore, this opinion on sections 143 and 188 is unfounded, baseless, misconceived and misplaced. It is one of the sources of confusions associated with the meaning of impeachment in the Nigerian context.

Thus, notwithstanding Justice Niki Tobi's assertion on impeachment in the context of the Nigerian Constitution above, it appears practically difficult even for him to avoid the word in his judgment.²⁵ A judge in the same case concluded that "impeachment means removal of an elected officer as used in the constitution" while another said that impeachment is recognized as one of the legitimate means by which a Governor or Deputy Governor, President or Vice President may be removed from office.²⁶ This fact is reiterated severally by the Nigerian Supreme Court in a plethora of subsequent judicial authorities. For instance, a justice of the Nigerian Supreme Court, Rhodes-Vivour JSC held that "...for an impeachment of a Governor or Deputy Governor of a State to be constitutional, there must be strict compliance with section 188 of the constitution..."²⁷ He went further to add at another breath that "...impeachment proceeding provided by section 188 of the constitution is purely a legislative constitutional affair..."²⁸ The judge here referred to section 188 of the Nigerian constitution as impeachment provisions. In fact, the instances are just too numerous to mention. Suffice it to say that there was no case brought pursuant to the provisions of section 188 or 143 of the Nigerian constitution in which no mention of it as impeachment provision was made. In view of the above, impeachment is provided for under sections 143 and 188 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999.

²⁴ Ibid, sections 146 and 191.

²⁵ He subsequently used impeachment and removal interchangeably in other places in the same judgment.

²⁶ See the judgments of Mustapher and Katsina Alu JJSC in *Inajoku v Adeleke* (note 20)

²⁷ *Danladi vs. Taraba State House of Assembly* (2015) 2 NWLR (pt.1442) 103 at 106.

²⁸ Ibid.

Another twist as to the usage of impeachment and removal under the constitution could be found in the provision which empowers the Vice President to take over from the President and Deputy Governor to succeed the Governor. In the provisions, the two terms were used in such a way as to give the wrong impression that impeachment and removal are two different ways through which the office of the President and the Vice President becomes vacant. It thus provides:

The Vice-President shall hold the office of President if the office of President becomes vacant by reason of death or resignation, **impeachment**, permanent incapacity or the **removal** of the President from office for any other reason in accordance with section 143 of this Constitution.²⁹

From the above provision, it is discernible that the office of the President and the Vice President becomes vacant as a result of death, resignation permanent incapacity and impeachment. These are the only causes for which the President or Vice President ceases to function in the office under the constitution.³⁰ The confusion is when the section added another clause which is “removal of the President from office for any other reason in accordance with section 143 of this constitution”. And section 143 of the constitution is the impeachment provision. This is where the problem of the meaning of the two terms lies as one is liable to misunderstand that impeachment is one way through which the President and the Vice President cease to function while removal in accordance with the provision of section 143 is another and different means.³¹

The way the constitution of Romania is couched reveals the understanding of the correct meaning of impeachment and removal and could serve as inspiration for Nigeria. It provides, in part, thus: “From the date of the impeachment until his/her eventual removal from office, the President is suspended by law from the exercise of his/her functions”. It is discernible from the above provision, and the heading of the provision which reads “impeachment”, that impeachment connotes the process while

²⁹ Section 146 (1) of the Constitution.

³⁰ See *Atiku Abubakar vs. Attorney General of the Federation & Ors* (2007) 6 NWLR (pt. 1031) 626

³¹ A similar provision could be found in respect of Governor and Deputy Governor of a state. See section 188 of the Constitution.

removal is the end-result.³² In the same vein, the constitution of Liberia makes similar provision which states: “The President and the Vice-President may be removed from office by impeachment for treason, bribery and other felonies, violation of the Constitution or gross misconduct”.³³

1.4 Usage of Impeachment in Judicial Processes

Apart from the constitutional provisions analyzed above, the judicial processes in Nigeria have sometimes contributed in no small measure in creating the confusion about the meaning of impeachment and removal. This is expressed in the court processes filed by lawyers, rulings and judgments of some courts. While this may be attributed to carelessness on the part of the courts and the lawyers, it sometimes arises out of sheer misunderstanding of what the two terms actually entailed. One of the earliest Nigerian judicial authorities on impeachment is the case of *Hon. Micheal Dapialong & Ors v Chief Joshua Dariye & Ors*.³⁴ In the judicial processes filed and the decision of the court, there were a lot of contradictions in the usage of the words “impeachment” and “removal” which gave rise to confusion as to their exact meaning. For instance, in formulating the sixteen questions for the court’s determination, the appellant’s counsel asked the court:

Whether the appointment, constitution and swearing in of the seven (7) man panel of the investigation by the first defendant herein and its entire proceedings leading to the purported **impeachment** of the plaintiff as the Governor of Plateau state in the unholy hours of Monday, 13th of November, 2006... ³⁵

This has clearly shown how the counsel misunderstood the meaning of impeachment. What really happened on the date he mentioned was not impeachment but the removal of the Governor. The impeachment started from the date the impeachment notice containing all the allegations against the Governor was presented to the Speaker of the House. This same misunderstanding was exhibited again by him in yet another question for determination as contained in his brief of argument. He posed, “whether

³² Article 97 of the Constitution of Romania, 1991.

³³ Article 62 of the Constitution of Liberia, 1986. Similar provisions could also be found under Articles 74, 86 and 88 of the Constitution of Lithuania, 1992.

³⁴ (2007) LPELR-SC.39/2007.

³⁵ Ibid

the purported **impeachment** of the plaintiff on Monday, the 13th day of November, 2006 by the 2nd to 7th defendants...”³⁶ This also makes one to understand that impeachment is the ultimate removal of the Governor in this case, and not the processes leading to his removal, which took place on the above mentioned date. On the other hand, the Supreme Court in its judgment as delivered by Mahmud Mohammed JSC, said “...as far as I am concerned, the main and crucial issue for determination in this appeal is whether the **removal or impeachment** of the first respondent in an impeachment proceedings...”³⁷ He went further to add that “... proceedings of the House which culminated in the alleged **removal or impeachment** of the first respondent. (Bold for emphasis). This shows that the words “removal” and “impeachment” were used interchangeably in the instances cited above which is a clear misunderstanding of their import. Similarly, in *All Progressive Congress v Peoples Democratic Party*,³⁸ one of the issues formulated by the respondent in his brief of argument was whether the impeachment of the appellant as the Governor of Ekiti State constituted a ground for his disqualification. This clearly shows that the respondent was referring to the removal of the appellant through impeachment. However, the way he used it clearly shows misunderstanding of the concept. So many of such instances abound which cannot be accommodated due to space constraints.

1.5 The Nature of Impeachment Proceedings in Nigeria

Impeachment proceedings arise in the exercise of the impeachment powers vested in the legislative arm of government by the constitution. There are always procedures to be followed for impeachment proceedings either laid down by the constitution or some other laws or both. Thus, a distinction had been drawn between what constitutes procedure and proceedings in this respect. The Supreme Court said:

Procedure is the set of actions necessary for doing something. It is also the method and order of directing business in an official meeting. On the contrary proceedings are the records of activities. Procedure generally comes before proceedings. In other words, proceedings are

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Mahmud Mohammed JSC in *Hon. Micheal Dapialong & Ors v Chief Joshua Dariye & Ors*, ibid

³⁸ (2015) 15 NWLR (pt. 342) 4

built on the procedure established for the particular activity or business.³⁹

From the above explanation, while impeachment procedure is the process to be followed for impeachment, impeachment proceedings are the activities that take place during the impeachment. But both the procedure and the proceeding culminate in the removal or acquittal of the subject of the impeachment. In view of this, what then is the nature of impeachment proceedings? There are virtually two divergent arguments as to the nature of impeachment proceedings. One is that it is a political proceeding while the other is to the effect that it is a semi-judicial or quasi-judicial proceeding. To those who see it as purely political proceeding, they hinge their argument on the fact that the legislature has a discretion as to whether to initiate the impeachment or not and what transpires before and after the proceedings involves a lot of politicking. Thus, it was opined long time ago that impeachments are “proceedings of a political nature...confined to political characters, to political crimes and misdemeanors, and to political punishments”.⁴⁰ Similarly, in impeachment proceedings, the fate of the public office holder who is the subject of impeachment is decided by men and women who are political beings.⁴¹

There is no doubt that the removal of an elected public officer by impeachment involves serious political considerations in the determination of whether or not to initiate the proceedings. This is because there may be many Presidents, and other public office holders, who may have acted contrary to the prescription of the law but have never been threatened with impeachment.⁴² And where the legislature decides to embark on impeachment of an elected public official, politics equally rears its ugly face to play a major role. Thus, a renowned author painted the picture in the following words, ‘The major problem with the impeachment process is that members of the congress are likely to feel tremendous pressure to forgo investigating President with high approval ratings or substantial popularity’.⁴³

³⁹ *Inakoju v Adeleke* (note 20)

⁴⁰ James Wilson, *The Works of James Wilson* (Chicago: Callaghan and Company, 1896) 408.

⁴¹ Micheal J. Gerhard, *The Federal Impeachment process: A Constitutional and Historical Analysis*, (2nd ed) (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2000) 67.

⁴² Jody C. Baumgatner, ‘Comparative Presidential Impeachment’ in Jody C. Baumgatner and Naoko Kada (eds) *Checking Executive Power: Presidential Impeachment in Comparative Perspective*, (Preager Publishers: Westport, 2003) 4.

⁴³ Micheal J. Gerhard, *The Federal Impeachment process: A Constitutional and Historical Analysis*, (2nd ed) (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2000) 67.

Similarly, politics play a major role in the decision of the lawmakers at the various stages of the impeachment proceedings in which numerical strength is required. This is why it was cautioned that “...and in such cases there will always be the greatest danger that the decision will be regulated more by the comparative strength of the parties than by the real demonstration of innocence or guilt”.⁴⁴

In the same vein, the attitude of the Nigerian courts from the 1980s to early 2000s clearly depicted impeachment proceedings as political in nature. This is because the courts had, during the period, avoided questions bordering on impeachment on the basis of political question doctrine.⁴⁵ Political question entails an issue over which jurisdiction is vested on the other branches of the government by the constitution⁴⁶ or a doctrine which attributes finality of an issue, omission or commission to the political department of the government and political party as enshrined under the constitution and the system of government in Nigeria.⁴⁷ Thus, under the Nigerian jurisprudence, it is a judicial principle that the internal proceedings of the legislature cannot be questioned in a court of law on the basis that it is a political question⁴⁸ provided that the legislature does not thereby breach any constitutional provisions.⁴⁹ This is in accord with separation of powers.⁵⁰ It is discernible that the internal affairs of the legislature which are not provided for either expressly or otherwise shall not be the concern of the court as such is regarded as political in nature. However, where it is so regulated by the law or the constitution like impeachment, the court is duty bound to inquire into it as such it is not political in nature. This is as laid down in the plethora of judicial pronouncements.⁵¹

⁴⁴ Alexander Hamilton, *The Federalist* (New York: Barnes and Nioble, 1961) 43.

⁴⁵ Nyinna Nwauche, ‘Is the End Near for Political Question Doctrine?’ (A Paper Presented at African Network for Constitutional Law Conference on Fostering Constitutionalism in Africa, Nairobi, Kenya, 2007) 3.

⁴⁶ Oba Popoola, ‘The Courts and the Democratic Process in Nigeria: An Appraisal of the application of some American Judicial Doctrines’ in Ajibade Bello (ed) *Law, Democratic Governance and Justice Administration in Nigeria*, (Ibadan: Life Gate Publishing Co. Ltd., 2009) 275.

⁴⁷ *Onuoha v Okafor* (1983) NSCC 494. See also the case of *Attorney General of Eastern Nigeria v Attorney General of the Federation* (1964) All NLR 218;

⁴⁸ See the cases of *Senate of the National Assembly v Tony Momoh* (1983) 4 NCLR 295; *Hon. Edwin Ume-Ezeoke v Alhaji Isa Makarfi* (1982) 3 NCLR 663; *Senator Okwu v Senator Joseh wayas* (1981) 2 NCLR 522.

⁴⁹ *Attorney General of Bendel State v The Attorney General of the Federation* (1982) 10 SC 1.

⁵⁰ *Inakoju v Adeleke* (note 20)

⁵¹ See for instance, *Ekenkhio v Egbadon* (1993) 7 NWLR (pt. 308) 717; *Asogwa v Chukwu* (2004) All FWLR (pt. 189) 1204; *Ndayeyo v House of Assembly* (1985) 6 NCLR 663.

Therefore, impeachment proceedings which are regulated by the constitution should not be so considered as political in nature. This is because, as the Supreme Court put it, the entire considerations may not be purely political as they may involve legal questions.⁵² In this respect, it is a legislative constitutional affair⁵³ because the power belongs to the legislature and it is provided under the constitution. More so, the whole arrangement of the impeachment proceedings before the impeachment panel is judicial-like. This is because it makes provision for the presentation of accusations against the subject of the impeachment and the observance of fair hearing. It is, thereafter, that the panel will make conclusion as to whether the allegations have been proved or not on the basis of the strength of the case presented by the parties involved. This makes impeachment proceedings quasi-judicial in nature.

In the light of the above, the view that impeachment proceeding is not political but quasi-judicial proceeding is more preferable. This is due to the simple reason that Nigerian courts had always insisted that legislative houses and investigation panels shall strictly observe all the aspects of fair hearing in impeachment proceedings. Thus, courts have intervened in most impeachment proceedings before and after removal of the office holders to ensure compliance with the constitution.

1.6 The Philosophical and Rationale Basis of Impeachment Power

The power of impeachment as vested on the Nigerian legislature by the constitution is based on a philosophy and rationale. First and foremost, it is intended to function as an instrument to check the excesses of the executive and in some dominions even the judicial arm of government.⁵⁴ This is on the basis of the principle of separation of powers which defends the society from impunity by any arm of government and make certain that each arm preserves its own sphere of influence.⁵⁵ So, the judiciary checks the exercise of powers by both the executive and the legislature by way of judicial review to guarantee that they function within their scope as provided by the

⁵² *Attorney General, Bendel State v Attorney General of the Federation* (1982) 3 NCLR 1; *Ezeoke v Makarfi* (1982) 3 NCLR 663

⁵³ In *Danladi v Taraba State House of Assembly* (2015) 2 NWLR (pt. 1442) 103 at 109, it was held that impeachment proceedings provided under section 188 of the constitution is a purely legislative constitutional affair.

⁵⁴ Section 6 (6) of the Constitution; *Adesanya v President of Nigeria* (1982) 2 NCLR 356

⁵⁵ Charles Arinze Obiora and Eze Malachy Chukwuemeka, 'Constitutionalism, Impeachment and Democracy in Nigeria: An Appraisal', *Journal of Constitutional Development*, (2012) 12 (1) 44-45.

constitution.⁵⁶ The executive, on the other hand, exercises some level of power over the judiciary in terms of appointment and discipline and over the legislature in cases of endorsement of legislations⁵⁷ and fiscal expenditure. The legislature also checks the judiciary in terms of endorsement of their appointment and financial expenditure⁵⁸ while the executive is exposed to the control of the legislature in case of expenditure and impeachment. Therefore, impeachment is a machinery meant to check the excesses in the exercise of the executive powers.⁵⁹ Furthermore, impeachment affords an opportunity to hold the elected executive responsible for misconducts committed while in office. In many jurisdictions that practice democracy across the globe, the President, Vice President and other members of the executive at the various levels of government enjoy legal protection from suits for their acts or omissions during the period they occupy the particular offices. In Nigeria, for instance, the President, Vice President, Governor and Deputy Governor enjoy such legal protection. Thus, no civil or criminal proceedings shall be instituted against them while in office.⁶⁰ This is immunity from legal proceedings which elected executive office holders subject to impeachment enjoy while in office.⁶¹ Therefore, impeachment presents itself as the only way to call elected executives to account for their wrongdoings in Nigeria during the pendency of their offices.⁶²

1.7 The Legal Effect of Impeachment

The constitutional provisions for impeachment do not clearly and sufficiently address some issues which mostly arise following removal as such are left to speculations, conjecture and misunderstandings. Such issues include the eligibility of a public officer to hold another or the same public office, prosecution and the entitlements

⁵⁶ See section 6 of the Constitution.

⁵⁷ *National Assembly v The President of Federal Republic of Nigeria* (2003) 41 WRN 94; Kehinde Mowoe, *Constitutional Law in Nigeria*, (Lagos: Malthouse Press, 2008) 26.

⁵⁸ Sections 80-84 of the Constitution.

⁵⁹ Kehinde Mowoe (note 56).

⁶⁰ See section 308 of the Constitution.

⁶¹ The concept of Immunity under the Nigerian constitution had received so much judicial interpretation in a lot of pronouncements from the Nigerian superior courts. See for instance the cases of *Tinubu v I.M.B. Securities Plc* (2001) All FWLR (pt.77) 1003; *Alameyeseigha v Yeiwa* (2002) All FWLR (t. 96) 552; *Media Tech Nig. Ltd., v Lam Adesina* (2005) 1 (t. 908) 461; *I C S Nig. Ltd. v Balton B. V.* (2003) 8 NWLR (pt. 822) 223; *Umnah v Attah* (2004) 7 (pt. 871) 63; *Alameiyeseigha v Federal Republic of Nigeria* (2006) 16 (t. 1004) 1; *Gani Fawehinmi v Inspector General of Police* (2002) All FWLR (pt. 108); *Global Excellence Communication Ltd. v Mr Donald Duke* (2007) 16 NWLR (pt. 1059) 22.

⁶² This is because the executive cannot be subjected to any legal process while holding the executive office. See section 308 of the Constitution.

which the office holders otherwise enjoy. The Nigerian constitution, unlike other jurisdictions, is silent on these issues. Therefore, the questions are left open for many interpretations. For, instance, the Lagos State House of Assembly passed a resolution in which they “pardoned” the State former Deputy Governor, who was impeached many years ago. The justification for the “pardon” is that he had shown remorse for his actions which resulted in his removal via the impeachment. And that the impeachment was not on any financial misconduct. This clearly shows lack of proper grasp of what exactly is the effect of removal through impeachment as it is currently under the Nigerian constitution. In fact, if the legislature, which is vested with the power of impeachment; will exhibit such “ignorance” what more of the ordinary man in the street?

Thus, the eligibility of the public officer removed through impeachment to occupy the same office or different office in the future had always attracted controversy. This has been recurrent whenever such persons attempt to contest or hold public office. Due to lack of clear provision on what becomes of the public officers concerned, the courts always had to be engaged in a legal battle as to what exactly is the position of the constitution on their eligibility. It is our contention that this was what made the Lagos State House of Assembly to “pardon” the Deputy Governor as pointed out earlier. This could be found in the House’s resolution which says “Pardon him and pass a vote of confidence on him as a fit and proper person that can be entrusted with political and administrative responsibilities”⁶³ and “to live a normal life”.⁶⁴

The issue of the prosecutions of the office holders after impeachment is also not categorically provided for as such is left to discretion. This arises when the grounds for impeachment amounted to offences under the criminal laws. In fact, there is no yet any public officer who has been successfully convicted of the offences for which he was impeached. All these issues would not have arisen if the constitution had made explicit provisions to address them. This is very unlike what obtains in other jurisdictions

⁶³ “Lagos Assembly Pardons Impeached Deputy Governor 8 Years After”, Premium Times, December 31, 2015, < <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/regional/ssouth-west/196006-lagos-assembly-pardons-impeached-deputy-governor-8-years-after.html> > accessed on May 17, 2025.

⁶⁴ “Impeachment of ex-Lagos Deputy Gov., Femi Pedro Invalidated”, Vanguard, December 31, 2015 <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2015/12/impeachment-of-ex-lagos-deputy-gov-femi-pedro-invalidated> accessed on May 13 2025.

where these issues have been categorically taken care of by the constitutional provisions.

The legal effect of successful impeachment is simply the removal of the elected office holders which cuts short their constitutionally recognized tenure. This means they cease to hold the offices they were elected even if it happened just a year or less in the four-year tenure. However, they may be reinstated to complete their tenure if the impeachment and removal are successfully challenged in court and the tenure does not elapse.⁶⁵ If the tenure elapses, they may be paid all their entitlements for the remainder of the tenure.⁶⁶ If, on the other hand, it is not successfully challenged in court, the office holders cease to hold the office and the tenure cut short by the removal is counted in the two-term maximum provided for them in the constitution.

1.8 Conclusion

It is found that the Nigerian constitution lacks precise provisions on the meaning of impeachment nor does it categorically even mention the word “impeachment” in its provisions relating to impeachment. This is the basis for the plethora of confusion and misunderstanding as to the exact meaning of impeachment in some judicial proceedings, legal discussions, media reportage and public analyses as pointed out earlier.

In the light of the foregoing, it is recommended that the Nigerian constitution should categorically use the word “impeachment” in the relevant provisions dealing with it in such a way as to bring out its clear meaning as a process for removal of public officers concerned. This will go a long way in reducing the misunderstandings associated with what actually impeachment entails and its relationship with removal. This may not necessarily require any much amendment or definition of the word as it could be achieved by simply inserting the word in the appropriate places. Thus, the side notes to the provisions of sections 143 (1) and 188 (1) should read “Impeachment of President or Vice President” and “Impeachment of Governor or Deputy Governor” respectively. The relevant text should also contain the word “impeachment” as follows:

Section 143 (1):

⁶⁵ *Ladoja v INEC* (2007) 12 NWLR (pt.1047); (2007) LPELR-CA/A/89/M/2007.

⁶⁶ See for instance *Nyako v Adamawa State House of Assembly* (2017) 6 NWLR (pt. 1562) 347.

*The President or Vice President may be removed from office **by impeachment** in accordance with the provisions of this section.*

(Bold for emphasis)

Section 188 (1):

*The President or Vice President may be removed from office **by impeachment** in accordance with the provisions of this section.*

(Bold for emphasis)

This appears in most state's constitutions in the United States like the Constitution of North Carolina which provides that "Removal of those officers from office for any other cause shall be by impeachment".⁶⁷ With the above amendment, it is categorically shown that impeachment means a process through which the President, Vice President, Governor or Deputy Governor could be removed.⁶⁸

Furthermore, it is found that the misunderstanding on the legal effect of impeachment is not unconnected to the silence of the constitution on the issue. There is no provision on what becomes of the office holder after his removal through impeachment. It is accordingly recommended that the constitution should provide that the removal of the office holders through impeachment does not subject them to any legal disability with a proviso that this does not prevent further prosecution of the office holders by the relevant agencies where the grounds for the impeachment constitute offences under the Nigerian law.

⁶⁷ Section 7 of the Constitution of North Carolina, 1868.

⁶⁸ Adrian Sgarbi, 'What's a Good Legislative Definition?' *Beijing Law Review*, (2013) 4 (1) 32; Akhil Reed Amar, 'On Impeaching Presidents', *Hofstra Law Review*, (1999) 28 (29) 323.